

8. M. KATO, H. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 99.
9. A. CHIESI VILLA, A. GAETANI MANFREDOTTI and C. GUASTINI, *Cryst. Struct. Commun.*, 1972, 1, 207.
10. Y. NISHIDA and S. KIDA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1979, 27, 275.
11. F. K. KNEÜBUHL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, 33, 1074.
12. D. W. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1970, 3108.
13. A. B. P. LEVER, 'Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy' Elsevier Pub. Company, Amsterdam, 1968, 204.
14. M. J. M. CAMPBELL and R. GRZESKOWIAK, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1967, 396.
15. I. M. PROCTER, B. J. HATHAWAY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1968, 1678.
16. B. J. HATHAWAY and D. E. BILLING, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1970, 5, 143.
17. R. J. DUDLEY and B. J. HATHAWAY, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1970, 1795.
18. A. CHIESI VILLA, A. GAETANI MANFRIDOTTI and C. GUASTINI, *Crys. Struct. Commun.*, 1972, 1, 125.

Magnetic and Spectroscopic Studies on Metal Complexes of N-Phenyl-N'-p-Bromophenyl Thiourea. Part I.

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THE following coordination compounds with N-phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea (L) have been prepared: $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$, ML_2X_2 [$M=Ni(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Mn(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $X=Cl$, NCS , OAc] and ML_4X_2 [$M=Ni(II)$, $Co(II)$, $Fe(II)$, $Mn(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Cd(II)$, $Hg(II)$ and $X=Cl$, NCS , NO_3]. The structure and bonding of the complexes have been studied by conductance data, magnetic susceptibilities, ir and electronic spectra. $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$ and ML_2X_2 types of complexes are tetrahedral whereas NiL_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 are square planar and octahedral respectively.

Experimental

Ferrous chloride was freshly prepared by the method described by Mellor¹. N-Phenyl-N'-p-bromophenyl thiourea was prepared by the method of Bhargava and coworkers².

Preparation of $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$, ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 complexes: Ethanolic solution of the metal chloride, nitrate, thiocyanate or acetate were mixed with the ligand (L) in 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 (M : L) molar ratio separately except in the case of $Hg(II)$ complexes which were prepared by mixing mercury salts and the ligand in acetone. The reaction mixtures were refluxed for 2-3 hrs. Excess of solvent was distilled off and the complexes were washed

with distilled water and a little ethanol. The complexes were dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$. Analytical data, melting points, magnetic moments and stereochemistry of the complexes are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND GENERAL BEHAVIOUR OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	m.p. (°C)	%Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		M	N	S	
NiL_2Cl_2	250	4.1 (4.3)	8.5 (8.2)	9.1 (9.4)	3.35
$NiL_4(NCS)_2$	135	4.1 (4.2)	9.8(10.0)	13.5(13.7)	3.36
CoL_2Cl_2	145	7.3 (7.6)	7.2 (7.5)	8.9 (8.7)	4.67
$CoL_2(NCS)_2$	146	7.2 (7.4)	10.3(10.6)	16.5(16.2)	4.65
CoL_4Cl_2	198	4.1 (4.3)	8.0 (8.21)	9.7 (9.4)	4.71
$CoL_4(NO_3)_2$	152	3.8 (4.1)	9.7 (9.9)	9.3 (9.1)	4.74
FeL_4Cl_2	130	4.0 (4.1)	8.0 (8.2)	9.6 (9.4)	5.40
MnL_2Cl_2	110	7.2 (7.4)	7.8 (7.6)	8.8 (8.6)	5.80
MnL_4Cl_2	111	4.3 (4.0)	9.6 (9.4)	8.5 (8.3)	5.67
ZnL_2Cl_2	82	8.5 (8.7)	7.2 (7.5)	8.3 (8.5)	dia
$ZnL_2(OAc)_2$	90	8.5 (8.2)	7.3 (7.0)	8.3 (8.0)	dia
ZnL_4Cl_2	92	4.9 (4.6)	9.7 (9.9)	4.8 (4.5)	dia
$Cd_2L_2Cl_4$	185	23.2(22.9)	8.0 (7.7)	6.7 (6.5)	dia
CdL_2Cl_2	200	14.3(14.1)	7.3 (7.0)	7.7 (8.0)	dia
$CdL_2(NCS)_2$	208	13.6(13.3)	9.7 (10.0)	15.0(15.2)	dia
CdL_4Cl_2	188	7.7 (8.0)	6.2 (5.9)	8.8 (9.1)	dia
HgL_2Cl_2	85	22.9(22.6)	6.2 (6.2)	7.5 (7.2)	dia
$HgL_4(NO_3)_2$	250	12.6(12.9)	9.3 (9.0)	8.5 (8.2)	dia

Molar conductance in nitrobenzene, ir spectra in nujol and electronic spectra (in nujol, ethanol or MgO) of the complexes were recorded.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are soluble in nitrobenzene. The low molar conductance values of $Cd_2L_2Cl_4$, ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 complexes show that these complexes are non-electrolytes³ having chloride, acetate, thiocyanate and nitrate coordinated to the metal ion. The magnetic data (Table 1) indicate tetrahedral geometry for ML_2X_2 and octahedral geometry for ML_4X_2 complexes⁴. ML_2X_2 and ML_4X_2 (with $M^{2+}=Zn, Cd$ and Hg) complexes are diamagnetic and show sp^3 and sp^3d^2 types of hybridization.

NiL_2Cl_2 shows the bands which can be assigned to the transitions: $15151 \ ^1A_{1g} \rightarrow \ ^1A_{2g}$ (ν_1), $20,000 \ ^1A_{1g} \rightarrow \ ^1E_g$ (ν_2) and $25,000 \ cm^{-1} \ ^1A_{1g} \rightarrow \ ^1B_{1g}$ (ν_3). The electronic spectra of the NiL_4Cl_2 and $NiL_4(NCS)_2$ complexes show three bands at 8696 and 8700 cm^{-1} , 13889 and 13900 cm^{-1} and 25640 and 25700 cm^{-1} respectively. The above bands may respectively be attributed to $^5A_{2g} \rightarrow \ ^5T_{2g}$ (F), $^5T_{1g}$ (F) and $^5T_{1g}$ (P) transitions in the octahedral environment of the metal ions. The bands observed at 5550 and 5600 cm^{-1} , 15100 and 15120 cm^{-1} in the spectra of CoL_2Cl_2 and $CoL_2(NCS)_2$ are due to the $^4A_g \rightarrow \ ^4T_1$ (F) and 4T_1 (P) transitions⁵ respectively. Three bands observed at 9600, 20000 and 21739 cm^{-1} in CoL_4Cl_2 and at 9616, 19607 and 21459 cm^{-1} in $CoL_4(NO_3)_2$ complexes are typical of $Co(II)$ complexes in octahedral⁶ environment and may be assigned to the transitions $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow \ ^4T_{2g}(F)$, $^4A_{2g}(F)$ and $^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. In FeL_4Cl_2 , a

TABLE 2—LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	10Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	β	β° (%)	ν_2/ν_1	λ (cm ⁻¹)	ζ_{sd} (cm ⁻¹)	LFSE (kJ mole ⁻¹)
NiL ₄ Cl ₂	8696	896	0.870	13.00	1.597	-399.7	799.4	128.55
NiL ₄ (NCS) ₂	8700	900	0.874	12.60	1.598	-407.3	814.6	124.80
CoL ₂ Cl ₂	3960	585	0.600	40.00	1.40	-200.10	600.3	56.81
CoL ₂ (NCS) ₂	3995	582	0.60	40.00	1.40	-200.60	601.8	58.27
CoL ₄ Cl ₂	10400	862	0.88	12.00	2.08	—	—	99.46
CoL ₄ (NO ₂) ₂	9991	814	0.84	16.00	2.03	—	—	95.55
FeL ₄ Cl ₂	10869	—	—	—	—	—	—	51.97

band appeared at 10869 cm⁻¹ and may be assigned to the ⁶T_{2g} → ⁶E_g(D) transition characteristic of O_h stereochemistry around the metal ion⁷. Using these assignments, the various ligand field parameters were calculated^{7,8} and are listed in Table 2.

The ir spectra of all the complexes of the ligand (L) follow a general pattern and detailed discussion have been made. The compound containing a thio-

amide moiety (H-N-C=S) have been studied by several workers and it has been suggested that all such compounds give rise to four thioamide bands^{9,10} in their ir spectra. The four thioamide bands are observed in the present ligand (L) at 1540, 1250, 1020 and 775 cm⁻¹. The high frequency N-H absorption bands in the substituted thioureas are not shifted much to lower frequencies indicating that nitrogen to metal bond is absent¹¹. The bands at 3200, 1600 and 1086 cm⁻¹ are due to ν_{N-H} , δ_{NH} and $\rho_{r,NH}$ ¹² respectively. Lowering of the frequency of C-S stretching vibrations indicates¹³ a weakening of the C=S and the strengthening of the C-N bond. The band¹⁴ $\nu_{N-C-N}(B_1)$ at 1540 cm⁻¹ in the ligand (L) is shifted to higher frequency regions in the complexes due to coordination through sulphur. Further, the double bond character of C-N bond is increased and confirms the M-S bonding in the complexes. A reverse change observed in thioamide, ν_{NH} , δ_{NH} , and $\rho_{r(NH)}$ modes in the Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes as compared to those discussed above suggest metal nitrogen bonding¹⁵. In the ZnL₂(OAc)₂ complex, two sharp bands appeared at 1720 and 1390 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to

$\nu_{as}(C \ll O)$, $\nu_s(C \ll O)$ vibrations¹⁶.

In the ir spectra of CoL₂(NCS)₂ and CdL₂-(NCS)₂ complexes, the ν_{CN} band occur at 2085 and 2070 cm⁻¹ respectively indicating M-NCS bonding¹⁶.

The ir spectra of CoL₄(NO₂)₂ and ZnL₄(NO₂)₂ complexes show the characteristic nitrate bands¹⁷ at 1280 and 820 cm⁻¹, 1285 and 825 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned as $\nu_{(NO_2)}$ and $\delta_{(NO_2)}$ respectively.

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References

- J. W. MELLOR, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1957, 5, 179.
- P. N. BHARGAVA and M. R. CHAURASIA, Ph.D. Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, 1968.
- W. J. GRARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 3119.
- E. J. DUFF, M. N. HUGHES and K. J. RUTT, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2499.
- F. A. COTTON, D. M. L. GOODGAME and M. GOODGAME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4690.
- R. W. MATTHEWS and R. A. WALTON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 1433.
- A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
- R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", An East West Edition, 1968, 411.
- E. LISBER, C. N. R. RAO, C. N. PILLAI and R. D. HITES, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1958, 36, 801.
- C. N. R. RAO and R. VENKATARAGHAVAN, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1952, 18, 541.
- G. F. SYAHOS, C. CURREN and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 6159.
- R. W. OLIFF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2037.
- A. U. MALIK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 1743.
- K. SWAMINATHAN and H. M. N. H. IRVING, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 26, 1291.
- R. RIVEST, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1962, 40, 2234.
- K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, N. Y., 1970.
- S. P. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARJEE and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 310.

Synthesis and Characterization of Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Iron(III) and Oxovanadium(IV) with New Tetradentate Schiff base

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In this note we report the synthesis and characterization of the Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III) and VO(II) complexes of the Schiff base ligand derived from 4-benzoyl-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and ethylenediamine.